

**Mercuration of Compounds containing the Reactive
Methylene (-CH₂-) group by means of
Mercuric Acetate.**

BY K. G. NAIK AND R. P. PATEL.

The mercuration of the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid and malonic acid was undertaken with a view to study the formation and the properties of the organo-mercury derivatives of compounds containing a reactive methylene group, and throw light, if possible, on the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of a reactive methylene (-CH₂-) group, situated between two carbonyl groups.

With this end in view, mercuric acetate was allowed to react in methyl alcohol with the following substances :

(1) Acetoacetanilide, (2) acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, (3) acetoacet-*m*-toluidide, (4) acetoacet-*p*-toluidide, (5) acetoacet- α -naphthylamide, (6) acetoacet- β -naphthylamide, (7) acetoacet-1:3:4-xylidide, (8) acetoacet-1:4:5-xylidide, (9) ethyl acetoacetate, (10) acetoacet-*m*-nitranilide, (11) ethyl malonate, (12) malonmono-phenylamide, (13) malonmono-*o*-toluidide, (14) malonmono-*m*-toluidide, (15) malonmono-*p*-toluidide, (16) malonmono- α -naphthylamide, (17) malonmono- β -naphthylamide, (18) malonmono-1:3:4-xylidide, (19) malonmono-1:4:5-xylidide and (20) malonamide.

Of these (18) and (19) were prepared for the first time by the modification of Whiteley's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 24).

It has been found that when mercuric acetate reacts with aromatic compounds, it introduces very easily the acetoxymercury (CH₃-COOHg-)group in the nucleus. It was, therefore, expected that in these reactions also, it would not only attack the methylene group, but also attack the aromatic part of these amides. Contrary to our expectations, it was found that mercuric acetate attacked the methylene group only, leaving the aromatic nucleus unaffected, even when mercuric acetate was employed in excess.

Whereas, the amides (1—11) reacted with mercuric acetate in methyl alcohol giving diacetoxymercury derivatives of the formula

(I); the amides (12—20) reacted under similar conditions, giving compounds of the general constitution (II).

(where R is H, Phenyl tolyl, or naphthyl etc. group).

All the above compounds are decomposed by dilute 0.25*N*-hydrochloric acid with the separation of the original amide. Hydrogen sulphide and ammonium sulphide decompose them with the precipitation of black mercuric sulphide. Potassium iodide decomposes the compounds with the liberation of alkali hydroxide. From these reactions, it appears that the linkage between the carbon atom of the reactive methylene group and mercury is a very weak one as is expected from compounds containing mercury attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a carbonyl group.

The general constitutions given to the above mercury compounds have been assigned from the following considerations.

(i) That the substituted group containing mercury has not replaced the hydrogen atom attached to a nitrogen atom of the NHR group (*i. e.*, it does not contain the N—Hg linkage), because, (a) malonic ester and acetoacetic ester which do not contain such a nitrogen atom do form similar compounds with mercuric acetate; (b) a compound containing N—Hg linkage behaves as a weak base, so much so, that its solution may be easily titrated against standard acid, using methyl orange as the indicator (*cf.* Ley and Kissel, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1357).

(ii) That the substituted grouping containing mercury has not replaced the aliphatic part of the molecule, for, (a) malonamide which does not contain such an aliphatic group, forms a similar mercury compound; (b) mercury compounds of aliphatic amines are not easily decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid, potassium iodide, and hydrogen sulphide; whereas the compounds described here are easily decomposed by these reagents giving the original amide.

(iii) That the substituted grouping containing mercury has not replaced the hydrogen atom of the nucleus, because, (a) malonamide, ethyl malonate and ethyl acetoacetate which do not contain such a nucleus, do form similar compounds; (b) from literature on mercury compounds, it appears that the mercury atom in the nucleus is not

removed by dilute hydrochloric acid, potassium iodide and hydrogen sulphide (cf. Schrauth and Bauerschmidt, *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 2740), while the mercury in these compounds is easily removed.

(iv) That the substituted grouping containing mercury is directly attached to the carbon atom of the methylene group, situated between two carbonyl groups, for, (a) the properties and the behaviour of compounds described here, are exactly similar to those having mercury attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a carbonyl group. It has been observed in case of mercurated 5-pyrazolone (which contains four acetoxymercury groups) that the mercury in position-4 (*i.e.*, attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a carbonyl group in position-5) is easily removed by dilute hydrochloric acid and hydrogen sulphide, the other three acetoxymercury groups, keeping firmly to their positions in the molecule (Schrauth and Bauerschmidt, *loc. cit.*). (b) On bromination of acetoxyhydroxymercurimalonamide, dibromomaltonamide is obtained.

Mercury compounds of the type (I) react with 10 p.c. sulphuric acid giving compounds of the following constitution :

They also react with an aqueous solution of potassium iodide with the separation of the original amide and the liberation of potassium hydroxide. The potassium hydroxide, liberated was found to be 2.013 equivalents, which according to theory should be 2 equivalents. These facts completely prove the constitution assigned to the compounds of the type (I).

Mercury compounds of the type (II), react with standard sodium hydroxide solution, giving a dihydroxymercury derivative. The quantity of sodium hydroxide required to completely hydrolyse the acetoxymercury ($-\text{CH}_3\text{COOHg}-$) group was found to be 1.12 equivalents which according to theory should be 1 equivalent. The constitution is further supported by the behaviour of the compounds with sulphuric acid. They give rise to hydroxysulphatomercury derivatives of the following constitution.

When hydroxyacetoxymercuri-*o*-toluidide is, however, made to react with an aqueous solution of potassium iodide, 2.97 equivalents of potassium hydroxide are liberated, which according to the theory should be 3 equivalents. This lends a further strong support to the correctness of the constitution assigned.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diacetoxymercuriacetoacetanilide.—Mercuric acetate (3.6 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol, was added to a methyl alcohol solution of acetoacetanilide (1 g.). The solution though clear at first became turbid on heating on a sand-bath for about 10 minutes. On cooling, a snow white crystalline product separated out. It was filtered and washed with water, alcohol and ether to remove the unreacted constituents. The product was insoluble in most of the ordinary organic solvents. It melts with decomposition at 204°. (Found: N, 2.23; Hg, 57.26. $C_{14}H_{15}O_6NHg_2$ requires N, 2.02; Hg, 57.72 per cent.).

The rest of the mercury derivatives have been similarly prepared by the interaction of mercuric acetate with the respective amides in methyl alcohol. The results are given in Table I.

Action of dilute hydrochloric acid.—The above mercury compound decomposed by hot 0.25*N*-hydrochloric acid with the separation of the original amide and mercuric chloride.

Action of potassium iodide.—The above compound (0.2627 g.) suspended in water, was treated with a solution of potassium iodide (1g.). Potassium hydroxide was at once liberated and titrated against 0.0574*N*-hydrochloric acid (of which 13.3 c.c. were required). It was subsequently heated for about 1 hour, but no further liberation of potassium hydroxide was observed.

Action of hydrogen sulphide.—The above mercury compound (0.491 g.) was suspended in water and heated to boiling. A slow current of hydrogen sulphide gas was passed into the solution till the complete precipitation of mercuric sulphide. Precipitates were then filtered through a Gooch crucible and washed with water, pyridine, carbon disulphide and alcohol to remove the amide formed during the course of the reaction as well as the sulphur which might have precipitated together with mercuric sulphide. It was then dried at 105-10°, and weighed (0.33 g.). (Found: Hg, 57.9. $C_{14}H_{15}O_6NHg_2$ requires Hg, 57.72 per cent.).

This indicated that the splitting up of the carbon—mercury linkage by hydrogen sulphide was quantitative.

Action of phenylhydrazine.—The substance decomposed on treatment with phenylhydrazine with the separation of grey metallic mercury.

Sulphatomercuriacetoacetanilide.—The above mercury compound (2 g.) was heated with 10 p. c. sulphuric acid on sand-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was then cooled, filtered and washed with water, alcohol and ether. The product was insoluble in most of the ordinary organic solvents. It turned brown at 240° but did not melt till 300°. (Found: Hg, 59.20; SO₄, 14.55. C₁₀H₉O₆NSHg₂ requires Hg, 59.61; SO₄, 14.3 per cent.).

Compounds similar to the above have been prepared by the action of sulphuric acid on compounds 1, 2, 3, 9, 12, and 20 of Table I.

The results are given in Table II. Compounds are numbered as 1a, 2a, 3a, 9a, 12a, and 20a.

Action of potassium iodide on diacetoxymercuriacetoacet-o-toluidide.—Diacetoxymercuriacetoacet-o-toluidide (1 g.) was treated with potassium iodide in water and heated to boiling. The liberated alkali was neutralised and the solution concentrated and cooled when crystalline needles of acetoacet-o-toluidide separated, m.p. 107°.

Action of dilute sodium hydroxide on acetoxyhydroxymercurimalonmonophenylamide.—The mercury compound (0.5038 g.) was treated with 50 c. c. of 0.018N-sodium hydroxide solution and refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was cooled, filtered and washed with water. The filtrate was then acidified with 10 c. c. of 0.1N-oxalic acid to neutralise the unreacted sodium hydroxide. The excess of oxalic acid was titrated against 0.018 N-sodium hydroxide (55 c. c.).

The insoluble product was found to be dihydroxymercurimalonmonophenylamide. (Found: Hg, 65.1. C₉H₁₀O₄N₂Hg₂ requires Hg, 65.57 per cent.).

Action of potassium iodide on Acetoxyhydroxymercurimalonmono-o-toluidide.—Acetoxyhydroxymercurimalonmono-o-toluidide (0.2127 g.) was treated with potassium iodide (1 g.) in water and boiled for 4 hours. The liberated alkali was neutralised by 0.0574 N-hydrochloric acid (16.5 c. c.).

Malonmono-1:3:4-xylylidide.—This was prepared by the modification of Whiteley's method (*loc. cit.*). Ethyl malonate (30 g.) and 1:3:4-xylylidide (15 g.) were put in a flask, fitted with a cork

through which passed a long bent tube and heated in paraffin-bath, at 120-25°. To get the maximum yield, the temperature was not allowed to go beyond 125°. After 8 hours, the contents of the flask were transferred to a glass-stoppered bottle and shaken for 4 hours with twice its volume of ammonia (d 0.88). The semi-solid mass was then allowed to evaporate and the residue was pressed on a filter and finally washed with ether to remove any of the unreacted ester and amine. It was then boiled with dilute alcohol (1:6) and filtered hot. The dixylidide and xylylamate remained on the filter undissolved. The filtrate on cooling separated malonmono-1:3:4-xylidide. The product when crystallised from the same solvent melts at 166°.

It is very soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetic acid, hot water, and sparingly soluble in cold water, hot benzene, but practically insoluble in petroleum. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.59 per cent.).

Malonmono-1:4:5-xylidide.—1:4:5-Xylidine (15 g.) and ethyl malonate (30 g.) were heated similarly for 8 hours at 120-25° as usual and subsequently treated as the preceding compound. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol (1:6), m.p. 197°. Solubility is similar to that of the preceding compound. (Found: N, 13.57. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.59 per cent.).

Action of bromine on acetoxyhydroxymercurimalonamide.—The mercury compound of malonamide was treated with an aqueous solution of bromine till no more bromine was absorbed. It was then heated to boiling when all the compound went in solution. The solution on cooling deposited a crystalline product which when filtered and washed with alcohol, melts at 203°. This was identical with the dibromomalonamide obtained by Freund (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 782).

TABLE I.
(A = Acetoxyhydroxymercurimalon-, D = diacetoxymercuryacetacet-.)

No.	Name.	Formula.	Colour changes.	M.p.	Analysis
					Found. Calc.
1.	D-anilide	$C_{11}H_{15}O_2NHg_2$	204° (decomp.)	Hg, 57.26 N, 2.23 57.72 P. c. 9.02
2.	D-c-toluidide	$C_{12}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	184°	Hg, 56.12 N, 2.07 56.57 1.98
3.	D-m-toluidide	$C_{12}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	194° (decomp.)	Hg, 56.21 56.57
4.	D-p-toluidide	$C_{12}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	181°.82°	Hg, 56.96 56.57
5.	D- α -naphthylamide	$C_{19}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	200° (decomp.)	Hg, 43.6 53.83
6.	D- β -do	$C_{19}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	197°	Hg, 43.4 53.83
7.	D-1- β -4-xylylide	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2NHg_2$	192°	Hg, 55.01 55.48
8.	D-1- β -5-xylylide	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2NHg_2$	204°	Hg, 55.00 55.48
9.	Ethyl-diacetoxymercury-acetoacetate	$C_{10}H_{14}O_7Hg_2$	Yellow and then reddish brown	does not melt till 300° decomp. above 200°	Hg, 61.7 61.9
10.	D-m-intranilide	$C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2Hg_2$	reddish brown liquid at 270°	decomp. above 200°	Hg, 54.44 54.2
11.	Ethyl-diacetoxymercury-malonate	$C_{11}H_{15}O_4Hg_2$	does not melt till 300° (decomp.)	Hg, 58.6 59.16
12.	A-monophenylamide	$C_{11}H_{13}N_2O_2Hg_2$	Turns yellow above 260°	" " decomp. till 300° decomposes above 270°	Hg, 60.9 61.35 60.00
13.	A-mono- <i>o</i> -toluidide	$C_{12}H_{14}O_2NHg_2$	N, 4.09 4.2
14.	A-mono- <i>m</i> -toluidide	$C_{12}H_{14}O_2NHg_2$	Yellow above 360° Brown at 280°	does not melt till 300°	Hg, 69.68 60.06
15.	A-mono- <i>p</i> -toluidide	$C_{12}H_{14}O_2NHg_2$	Reddish brown above 280°	Hg, 69.90 60.00
16.	A-mono- α -naphthylamide	$C_{19}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	278° (decomp.)	Hg, 46.54 56.28
17.	A-mono- β -naphthylamide	$C_{19}H_{17}O_2NHg_2$	275° (decomp.)	Hg, 47.4 56.98
18.	A-mono-1- β -4-xylylide	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2NHg_2$	Yellow above 250°	270° (decomp.)	Hg, 58.35 58.82
19.	A-mono-1- β -5-xylylide	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2NHg_2$	Yellow above 260 and Brown at 275°	Hg, 59.04 58.82
20.	A-amide	$C_8H_5O_2NHg_2$	does not melt till 800°	Hg, 69.9 69.44

TABLE II.

(S = Sulphatomercuri-acetoaccb).

No.	Name.	Formula.	Colour change.	M.p.	Analysis.	
					Found. Calc.	
1a.	S-anilide	$C_{10}H_9O_2NSHg_2$	Brown at 240°	Did not melt till 300°	Hg, 59.3 SO ₄ , 14.55	59.61 p.c. 14.30
2a.	S-o-toluidide	$C_{11}H_{11}O_2NSHg_2$	Brown above 240°	SO ₄ , 14.25	14.01
3a.	S-p- do	$C_{11}H_{11}O_2NSHg_2$	Brown above 250°	Did not melt till 300°	SO ₄ , 14.6	14.01
9a.	Ethyl sulphatomercuriacetoacetate	$C_6H_8O_7SHg_2$	Yellow above 200°, reddish brown at 230°	SO ₄ , 14.7	15.3
12a.	Hydroxysulphatomercuri-malon-mono-phenylamide	$C_{18}H_{18}O_{10}N_4SHg_4$	Yellow above 250° brown at 255°	Hg, 62.53 SO ₄ , 8.1	62.4 7.49
20a.	Hydroxysulphato-mercury-malonamide	$C_8H_{10}O_{10}N_4SHg_4$	does not decompose till 300°	Hg, 70.4 SO ₄ , 7.9	70.8 8.49

The authors take this opportunity to express their gratitude to the Government of His Highness the Maharaja Gaekwar of Baroda for a grant which defrayed the expenses incurred in this work.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
BARODA COLLEGE, BARODA.

Received March 19, 1952.